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PREDICTORS AND FEATURES OF POST-COVID SYNDROME DEVELOPMENT (LITERATURE OVERVIEW)

Abstract.

The article is devoted to analyzing scientific research on the long-term consequences of COVID-19 - post-COVID syndrome. The persistence of symptoms that occurred during the acute phase of COVID-19 for more than 12 weeks and can not be explained by other alternative diagnoses has been officially defined as post-COVID syndrome. The analysis found that the average duration of COVID-19 symptoms was 80 days from the onset. At least one symptom persisted for a long time in 87% of patients, and 55% of study participants had three or more symptoms. On average, the quality of life after COVID-19 deteriorated in 44% of patients, with many patients experiencing fatigue (53.1%), shortness of breath (43%), joint pain (27%), and chest pain (22%). The main predictors of post-COVID syndrome include the severity of the primary infection, age and gender, comorbidities, autoimmune processes, mental disorders, gut microbiota disorders, cytokine storm, and socioeconomic status.

Purpose: *to determine the predictors and features of the clinical development of post-COVID syndrome in patients with COVID-19.*

Materials and Methods: *a retrospective analysis of scientific literature sources PubMed, Cochrane Library, and ScienceDirect was conducted.*

Keywords: *COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, post-COVID syndrome, "long-haulers".*

Introduction. COVID-19 is a disease caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, which causes respiratory illness in humans, including COVID-19 acute respiratory disease, and can be transmitted from person to person. This virus was first identified during the investigation of an outbreak in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. The SARS-CoV-2 virus belongs to the Coronaviridae family, which includes more than 40 varieties of coronaviruses that can infect birds and mammals. Coronaviruses are complex enveloped viruses with single-stranded RNA. According to electron microscopy, virions are approximately 100-120 nm in size and have a bilipid membrane, the supercapsid envelope. Peplomers extend from the surface of the envelope, creating the impression of a crown on the surface of the virion, hence the name "coronaviruses". Peplomers play a special role in the ability of the virus to penetrate deep into the cell for further reproduction.

Spread occurs through close contact between people, mainly through respiratory droplets released when an infected person coughs, sneezes, sings, exercises, or talks. Spread occurs through large respiratory droplets that can travel short distances and settle directly on the surface of a person's mucous membrane, or through small respiratory aerosol particles that can stay in the air for several hours and travel long distances (> 2 meters) before inhaling. The virus can also be spread through contact with surfaces contaminated with respiratory secretions, if a person touches a contaminated surface and then comes into contact with the mucous membranes of the face (eyes, nose, mouth).

The severity and combination of clinical symptoms vary among people with COVID-19. Some people have few or no symptoms, while others are severely ill and die. Most people who have had COVID-19 make a full recovery, but it is estimated that about 30-43% of people have various long-term effects.

A recent analysis showed that one in ten people had COVID-19 for more than three weeks after the onset of symptoms. The medical literature has coined a term that characterizes such patients as "long-haulers," who are divided into two groups: people who, after suffering COVID-19, have objective pathological changes in the cardiovascular, nervous, gastrointestinal, excretory, respiratory, and hemostatic systems and people who have symptoms of coronavirus infection for a long time without a morphological basis. The persistence of symptoms that occurred during the acute phase of COVID-19 for more than 12 weeks and cannot be explained by other alternative diagnoses has been officially defined as post-COVID syndrome (PCS).

To define the term "long-term covid", 3 consecutive stages after infection with COVID-19 are used (according to the UK National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guideline "Management of the long-term effects of COVID-19" (NG188)): Acute COVID-19 - signs and symptoms of COVID-19 within 4 weeks; Prolonged symptomatic COVID-19 - signs and symptoms of COVID-19 from week 4 to week 12; Post-COVID syndrome - signs and symptoms that occur during or after COVID-19 infection, last more than 12 weeks and are not explained by another diagnosis.

The main part. After analyzing numerous studies on the consequences of COVID-19, it was found that the most common long-term symptoms are cough, sub-febrile fever, and severe weakness. Additional symptoms include increased heart rate, myalgias, arthralgias, headache, chest pain, shortness of breath, loss of taste or smell, blurred vision, hearing loss, tremors, numbness in the extremities, mobility disorders, skin rashes, gastrointestinal disorders, memory loss, mood changes, neurocognitive impairment, and mental disorders (anxiety, depression).

One study conducted in Rome, Italy, involving 143 patients with an average age of 57 years, clarified the presence of symptoms after a 2-week hospitalization for COVID-19. The average duration of symptoms was 80 days from the onset of the disease. At least one symptom persisted for a long time in 87% of patients, and 55% of study participants had three or more symptoms. On average, the quality of life deteriorated in 44% of patients, with many patients experiencing weakness (53.1%), shortness of breath (43%), joint pain (27%), and chest pain (22%). Symptoms of acute disease were absent in all patients.

In another study, conducted through an online survey conducted by the online support group Body Public COVID-19, which has experience in conducting such surveys, 640 responses were received from respondents whose symptoms persisted for more than 2 weeks. The symptoms reported by the survey participants were varied. The main symptoms reported by more than 70% of respondents were shortness of breath, chest tightness, fatigue, chills, body aches, dry cough, fever, headache, dizziness, and decreased concentration. Between 40 and 50% of respondents reported severe fatigue that prevented them from even getting out of bed, severe headaches, fever, and loss of taste or smell. Some patients noted that symptoms worsened in the evening or during physical activity during the day. Approximately 10% of respondents recovered in an average of 4 weeks. In 90% of those patients who did not recover in 4 weeks, symptoms were observed for an average of 40 days. A significant number of respondents had symptoms for 5-7 weeks. According to experts, the probability of full recovery in 50 days was below 20%.

Scientists identify predictors of post-COVID syndrome, including: severity of primary infection (patients who have experienced severe COVID-19 with hospitalization and the need for oxygen therapy are at increased risk of developing PCS); age: older people and children are more susceptible to long-term effects of COVID-19; comorbidities the presence of chronic diseases (cardiovascular, pulmonary, diabetes, obesity) before COVID-19 infection increases the risk of developing ACLs; mental disorders: depression, anxiety and post-traumatic stress disorder that may develop after COVID-19 can exacerbate after COVID symptoms; immunological predictors: autoimmune

processes (some studies indicate the possibility of developing autoimmune reactions after COVID-19, which may contribute to the development of ACLs); cytokine storm - a strong inflammatory response to the virus leads to damage to organs and tissues, which in turn can contribute to the development of PCS; gut microbiota disorders: changes in the gut microbiota after COVID-19 affect the immune system and contribute to the development of a chronic inflammatory response; other factors: gender (women are more likely to report long-term symptoms after COVID-19); socioeconomic status: people with low socioeconomic status may have limited access to healthcare and poorer living conditions, which can worsen the course of the disease and increase the risk of developing PCS.

Conclusions. Thus, after analyzing various modern scientific studies on the consequences of COVID-19, we found that the most common manifestations of post-COVID syndrome are: weakness, shortness of breath, chest pain or tightness, cough, tremors, and numbness in the limbs, memory loss, frequent mood changes, anxiety, depression, decreased concentration, dizziness. The main predictors of post-COVID syndrome are the severity of the primary infection, age, comorbidities, autoimmune processes, mental disorders, gut microbiota disorders, cytokine storm, gender, and socioeconomic status.

References:

1. Coronavirus Updates: The Illness Now Has a Name: COVID-19. The New York Times. Available at <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/02/11/world/asia/coronavirus-china.html>. February 11, 2020; Accessed: Feb. 11, 2020.
2. Gorbalenya A.E. Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus —The species and its viruses, a statement of the Coronavirus Study Group. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.07.937862>. Feb. 11, 2020; Accessed: Feb. 13,2020.
3. World Health Organization. Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV)
4. Ramzy A., McNeil D.G. W.H.O. Declares Global Emergency as Wuhan Coronavirus Spreads. The New York Times.
5. CDC. 2019 Novel Coronavirus, Wuhan, China: How it Spreads. CDC.
6. Hui D.S., Azhar E., Madani T.A., Ntoumi F., Kock R., Dar O. et al. The continuing 2019-nCoV epidemic threat of novel coronaviruses to global health —The latest 2019 novel coronavirus outbreak in Wuhan, China.
7. Johnson AG, Amin AB, Ali AR, et al: COVID-19 incidence and death rates among unvaccinated and fully vaccinated adults with and without booster doses during periods of delta and Omicron variant emergence — 25 U.S. Jurisdictions, April 4–December 25, 2021. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 71:132–138. 2022. doi: 10.15585/mmwr.mm7104e2